

FIRE AND MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF CO-BLENDED UNSATURATED POLYESTER/PHENOLIC RESIN MATRICES AND DERIVED GLASS-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Unsaturated polyester (UP) based glass fibre reinforced polymer composites (GFRC) are intensively used in many applications due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, low cost, good corrosion and chemical resistance and low maintenance requirements. Despite these advantages, poor fire resistance, the evolution of smoke and emission of styrene while burning of UP based composites are major limiting factors for applications where fire safety is important.

The intrinsic flammability property of UP could be altered either by chemical modification of the resin or by adding flame retardant chemicals into it. In the chemical modification of the resin, flame retardant elements such as halogen or phosphorous are introduced in the UP resin backbone. The presence of halogen in UP resin or the curing agent, styrene significantly improves the flame retardancy of UP, but while it burns the presence of halogen raises environmental issues [1-3]. Commonly used flame retardants such as alumina trihydrate (ATH), magnesium hydroxide and calcium carbonate can be used, however to be effective, they are required in high concentration (typically >30% w/w), which can affect, mechanical properties of the composite [4].

The physical blending of resins is recognised as simple and effective method by which the composition may gain the favourable properties of each component [4]. For example, phenol formaldehyde (PH) resin has excellent flame

retardance, good heat resistance, and low smoke/toxic gas evolution on burning [5] than UP. However the brittleness of the PH based composite laminate is the major limiting factor for their use in structural composites. The physical blending of these two different types of resin may form semi interpenetrating networks (IPNs) or hybrid polymer networks (HPNs). The degree of the network interpenetration depends upon the viscosity of the two resins, dispersivity, compatibility and the curing rate.

The main aim of this work is to improve fire resistance of UP by blending it with PH [6, 7]. The main problem of blending UP and PH resins is their incompatibility due to their different curing mechanisms, which can lead to phase separation and hence, poor mechanical properties of the composite produced. The compatibility can be improved by functionalizing one of the resins [7]. In this work, we have used an allyl-functionalised resole PH to produce compatible blend with a UP resin. The compatibilization between two resins has been studied by DSC (differential scanning calorimetry) and DMA (dynamic mechanical analysis). Cast resins have been prepared from UP, PH and blended resins and their fire performance studied. GFRCs from UP and UP/PH resin matrices have been prepared and their fire and mechanical performance were studied.

2 Experiments

2.1 Materials

Unsaturated Polyester (UP): Crystic® 2.406PA, Scott Bader.

Radical Catalyst: Catalyst M (Methyl Ethyl Ketone Peroxide based), Scott Bader.

Phenolic resin (PH): Methylon 75108, Sumitomo Bakelite Europe N.V (allyl functionalized resole type phenolic resin solvent free)

Fibre reinforcement: Woven roving E-glass fibre (300 gm/m², Glasplies)

2.2 Sample Preparations

Cast resin samples were prepared by using UP, PH and UP/PH blended resins. The blends of varying UP/PH ratios were prepared by mixing required quantities of UP and the PH resin as in Table 1 with mechanical stirring and then degassing under vacuum for 15 min. A methyl ethyl ketone catalyst (2 wt % w.r.t. resin) was added into the resin mixture and stirred for another 10 min. Subsequently the resins were transferred to the square shaped moulds (100mm x100 mm), cured at room temperature for 24h and post cured step by step up to 190°C (Table 1). The cured samples were of ~3.0 mm thicknesses.

GFRC were prepared by using UP and UP/PH blends as matrices prepared as mentioned above. Eight layers of woven E-glass fabric, impregnated individually with resin (50% each by weight), were stacked, vacuum bagged and cured using similar curing conditions as cast resins (see Table 1). The GFRC of pure PH could not be prepared because of its low viscosity at high temperatures, there was too much leak-out.

2.3 Characterization and Testing

2.3.1 Curing behaviour and compatibility study

A DSC Q2000 was used to test the samples (2-10 mg) at a heating rate of 5°C/min within the range of 30-350°C. The curing peaks and heat of reaction during curing (J/g) from the curves were measured.

A DMA Q800 was used to test the samples using a single cantilever clamp and multi-frequency-strain experiment set up (0.1% strain and 1 Hz frequency). The specimen was heated at 10°C/min within the range 30-350°C. Tan δ and storage modulus were measured and recorded. For each sample two test specimens were tested.

2.3.2 Flammability behaviour study

Limiting Oxygen Index (LOI)

The limited oxygen index (LOI) of cured unsaturated polyester, resole phenolic and co-blended cast resin samples were studied using Stanton Redcroft apparatus equipped with an oxygen analyser. Three test specimens of ~ 3 mm thickness, 10 mm width, and 100 mm length were cut from the cured resins. The sample was suspended vertically and ignited with a flame. The condition at which the sample just burnt like candle was used to determine the LOI value of that particular sample.

Cone Calorimetry

The flammability of all cast resin samples UP, PH and UP/PH blends were evaluated in a cone calorimeter (Fire Testing technology, UK). Three specimens of each sample of 100 x 100 mm x ~ 3mm were fire tested by exposing them to 50 kW/m² incident heat flux in the horizontal mode with an ignition source.

UL-94 flammability test

A standard method UL-94 (ISO 1210) test was used to classify the GFRCs samples according to the standard open flame. The samples were tested under vertical and horizontal UL-94 modes and the burning rates were also noted.

2.3.3 Mechanical performance study

Tensile Testing

The tensile tests of the GFRC specimens (200 mm x20 mm x ~3 mm) were conducted using a 50kN load cell attached to a Universal Instron 3369 tensometer frame with 1mm/min crosshead speed. The reported results are average of three replicate tests.

Flexural Testing

The flexural moduli of the GFRC specimens (200 mm x 20 mm x ~3.0 mm) were measured in three-point bending mode using a 50kN load cell attached to a Universal Instron 3369 tensometer. The specimens were tested in the displacement-controlled mode (i.e., crosshead speed of 1 mm/min). The reported results are averages of three replicate tests.

Impact Testing

The impact (dynamic) moduli of the GFRC specimens (100 mm x 100 mm x ~3.0 mm) were measured in Instron Dynatup instrument with 100mm falling height and 1.02 kg mass.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Curing and compatibility study by DSC

The DSC curves have been used to study the curing behaviour of resins such as temperature range for curing, cure peak temperature, percentage of cure etc. This information has been used to optimize cure conditions for resins and composites (Table 1); and also to study the compatibility of the component resins in the blends.

The DSC of uncured UP in Figure 1 shows the exothermic curing reaction of the resin starting at room temperature and peaking at 82°C with 282 J/g heat release. Phenolic resins typically show an exothermic peak at much higher temperature than UP [8-10], for the resin used here the initiation of curing is at 180°C and peak maximum 230°C (Figure 1) with a total heat release of 231J/g. The curing of phenolics occurs by polycondensation, producing water and formaldehyde, which evaporates endothermically. The endothermic peak in this case was masked by a much larger exothermic peak. This suggests that UP resin can be cured at room temp and then post cured at 80 °C (curing peak temperature of UP) with a radical initiator. Whereas, PH needs a higher temperature of 180°C for curing and 230°C for post curing without an initiator. The DSC curve of uncured UP/PH: 50/50 shows several peaks, a first large exothermic peak

(Peak max =76 °C), which can be assigned to the radical curing reaction of UP (106 J/g) and a second large peak maximum at 226°C assigned to the curing of PH 433J/g. A third very small peak can also be observed peaking around 170-180°C with a total heat release of 31J/g. Such a peak was found neither in the DSC curve of the uncured PH (performed without a radical initiator) nor in that of UP. This suggests that a new reaction is occurring which most probably involves radical reactions of the allyl groups of the PH. This suggests an interaction between the two networks in UP/PH blended resin. Moreover, the blended resin was completely cured at 190 °C, whereas 100% curing in phenolic resin could only be achieved by post curing up to 230 °C.

3.2 Differential Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

All cast resin samples reported in Table 2 were tested by DMA. The variation of the storage modulus with temperature was used to confirm the curing of the cast resins and the Tan δ was used to determine the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the cured pure resins and blends. DMA was also used to explore the compatibility of the blends [11].

The storage modulus of blended resin decreased with increase of temperature indicating the completion of curing as shown in Figure 2. The differences in the behaviour between UP and PH resins were observed in DMA curves. The UP shows sudden and significant decrease of storage modulus from room temperature upto 95°C (T_g of UP), the decrease is much gradual in PH, occurring around 230°C as a result of higher T_g . The blend UP/PH: 50/50 displays the higher storage modulus at room temperature with a value similar to that of PH, shows significant decrease of storage modulus from room temperature up to 130°C (T_g of UP/PH:50/50) and behaves similar to UP resin.

Figure3 shows the graph of Tan δ as a function of temperature. Both pure resins display a single peak, corresponding to a single T_g of the respective resin. All blends show one T_g value, indicating the compatibility of two resins. During curing of the blends, cross linking between the UP and

PH through the allyl functional groups takes place and an inter penetrated network (IPN) structure is formed [12, 13].

UP and PH have T_g of 94°C and 287°C, respectively. The T_g of the blends is in between these two values and increases with increasing PH content (see Table 2). The DMA results hence, corroborate the observation from DSC result that there is a possible cross linking reaction between the two resins and confirm that the two resins have compatibility and the blended resin acts as a single material.

3.3 Flammability behaviour of cast resin

In order to understand the effect of phenolic resin content on the flammability of the blended cast resins, all samples listed in Table 1 were tested as discussed below:

Limiting Oxygen Index (LOI)

The limiting oxygen index (LOI) is the minimum concentration of oxygen, expressed as a percentage that will support combustion of a polymer. Resistance to flaming increases as value of LOI increases. The LOI values of all samples are given in Table 2. The Δ LOI (the difference between LOI of the sample and that of UP) as a function of versus increasing phenolic content is shown in Figure 4.

The pure UP resin is combustible and has LOI value of 18 %. Phenolic resin has a higher LOI value, 22.2 %, indicating its less flammability than unsaturated polyester. The LOI value of phenolic however, is lower than expected from a phenolic resin. The lower flammability of phenolics is due to their chemical structure, having greater number of stable aromatic benzene rings [9,10] which on heating cross-link and char, whereas in UP, the resin decomposes into combustible volatiles, which burn. The flammability behaviour of the co-blended sample is in between that of the neat UP and neat phenolics as shown in Figure.4. In the presence of phenolic resin in the blended samples have shown increase in the LOI values up to 19.6 % for UP/PH: 50/50 blend which

was achieved by the char yielding property of phenolics. The LOI values increased with increasing phenolic content as can be seen from Figure 4. It must be emphasized that the flammability of blended samples is not dependant on one only factor i.e, cross linking phenolic groups, but also on other factors such as viscosity of resins during blending, dispersivity, compatibility between the resins, curing rate and nature of IPN structure.

Cone calorimetry

The heat release rate (HRR) , rate of smoke release (RSR) and % mass versus time curves are plotted in Figures 5 (a),(b) and (c), while all derived parameters i.e. time-to-ignition (TTI), flame out time (FO), peak heat release rate (PHRR), total heat release (THR), effective heat of combustion (EHC), total smoke released (TSR) and % residual weight are given in Table 3.

According to the results shown in Table 3, the UP ignited earlier (39s) than pure phenolic resin (49s) TTI of phenolic resin is also very low, indicating that despite phenolic's expected inherent flame retardant, the resin used here is combustible and ignites within a short period of time However, once ignited, it burns slowly (flame out 218 s) with lower heat release rate as in Figure 5(a) compared to UP (FO = 180s). The PHRR from phenolic (720 kW/m²) is much lower than from UP (1130 kW/m²); THR is also lower (Ph = 54.7MJ/m², UP = 87.2 MJ/m²). This is due to intrinsic chemical structure of phenolic resin as explained in previous section. Phenolic resin during combustion undergoes cross-linking reactions leading to char formation [14,15] as shown in Table 3, the char yield of phenolic is 21%, whereas UP has only 1.7%. The blended resins have shown lower PHRR than pure UP (see Table 3), the value decreasing with increasing phenolic content. Similar trend is shown for THR. This can be explained due to the char formation tendency of phenolics [15], the char layer act as a thermal barrier, slowing down the further burning of sample [16].

As can be seen from Figure 5(b), the total smoke released from phenolic resin is lower than that of UP resin. In unsaturated polyester resin the aromatic contents with styrene and phthalic acid functionalities cause significant smoke production, whereas, phenolic resin contains stable aromatic benzene ring in its structure which is less reactive with oxygen. UP/PH blends have TSR values in between UP and PH, the value decreases with increasing PH content.

The effective heat of combustion (heat released from a burning test specimen in a given time interval divided by the mass lost from the test specimen in the same time) does not show much difference and it is in the range of 19-20MJ/kg for all samples.

3.4 Flammability behaviour of composite laminates

The flammability of composite laminates (GRFC) produced from resins in Table 1 were studied by UL-94 test, used commercially as a quality control test. Results of GRFC samples are given in Table 4. All samples failed in both vertical and horizontal burning test. In each case the whole sample burnt after the first ignition. To compare their burning behavior, burning rate was also measured. As can be seen from Table 4, the burning rates in horizontal and vertical test for UP is higher than for blended samples. In vertical orientation, the UP laminate has a 70mm/min burning rate whereas UP/PH: 50/50 has a 32mm/min, with > 50 % reduction. These results are showing the same trend as observed from cast resin samples from LOI and cone results. As explained in Section 2.2 a composite laminate from pure phenolic could not be prepared.

3.6 Mechanical Properties of UP/PH blended resin composite laminates

The flexural, tensile and impact moduli normalized with respect to fibre volume fraction of all samples are given in Table 5. The stress-strain curve of the GRFCs under tensile mode are shown in Figure 6. The slope of stress-strain curves for pure UP and the co-blended resin matrix GRFCs were similar. The tensile modulus of GRFC of UP was 13.3 GPa and for UP/PH the

value varies from 12 to 13.8 GPa depending on the blend ratio. The value is lower than UP, however not significantly lower, which is as expected as tensile properties are fibre dependent. Some reduction observed could be due to lower fibre-resin interface bonding in some cases. Moreover, there does not seem to be an obvious trend of change of value, with increasing content, indicating that this is due to individual sample preparation rather than due to the phenolic content.

The effect of phenolics in the blended resin matrix of GRFC on mechanical properties was also observed in flexural mode in term of flexural modulus as shown in Table 5. The flexural modulus of up UP laminate was 17.0 GPa while in blended samples it is reduced to ~ 15.7-16 GPa. The value is reduced, but not to a large extent as was expected from the brittle nature of phenolics. This could be that the UP chains may have a plasticizing effect on the phenolic resin leading to a fall in viscosity of the system. This might make the physical escape of volatile matter from the resin easier to produce samples without voids, resulting in retaining good mechanical properties [17].

The Impact modulus of laminates samples are reported in Table 5. Impact modulus of UP laminate was 13.1 GPa and for the co-blended samples of UP/PH: 70/30, 60/40 and 50/50 were 13.7, 14.0 and 13 GPa respectively. The phenolic content has not adversely affected the impact properties similar to those of flexural.

The results of mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced composites in Table 5 has shown that the inclusion of functionalized phenolic in UP has not significantly affected all mechanical properties of UP. This is due to the formation of ester linkages by the reaction of UP with the resol resin prevents the generation of dimethylene ether linkages. This may further reduce the amount of methylene bridges and the liberation of formaldehyde and yield good mechanical properties into the co-blended samples [17].

4 Conclusions

The UP/allyl-functionalised PH co-blended resin systems with different ratios have shown good compatibility. The interaction between UP and PH was improved by the presence of allyl-functional groups in the PH which formed the cross linkages between UP and PH by chemical interaction and also helped to form well-built IPN structure by physical interaction.

The LOI, UL-94 and cone calorimetric results have shown that the presence of PH in the UP/PH co-blended resin improved the fire retardancy of the blended material. The flammability of the blends decreased with increasing phenolic content.

The UP/allyl-functionalised PH co-blended resin systems with different ratios have shown improved fire retardancy without having any detrimental effect on their mechanical properties.

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Fig.1.DSC curves of UP, PH and UP/PH uncured resin

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Table1. UP,PH and UP/PH cast resin formulation

Sample	UP (wt %)	PH (wt %)	Cat.M (wt % UP)	Curing conditions
UP	100	-	2	RT 24h, 80°C 6h
UP/PH:80/20	80	20	2	50° C (6 h), 80° C(12h),120° C (3h),190° C (4h)
UP/PH:70/30	70	30	2	50° C (6 h), 80° C(12h),100° C (8h), 120° C (6h),130° C (2h), 150° C (2h),180° C(2h)
UP/PH:60/40	60	40	2	50° C (6 h), 80° C(12h),100° C (8h), 120° C (6h),130° C (2h), 150° C (2h),180° C(2h)
UP/PH:50/50	50	50	2	50° C (6 h), 80° C(12h),100° C (8h), 120° C (6h),130° C (2h), 150° C (2h),180° C(2h)
PH	-	100	-	100° C (8h), 120° C (6h),130° C (2h), 190° C(2h)

Fig. 2. Storage Modulus as function of temperature of UP, PH and UP/PH: 50/50 cast resin

Table 2. T_g and LOI of cast resin

Sample	T_g (°C)	LOI (%)
UP	94	17.9
UP/PH:70/30	110	19.0
UP/PH:60/40	117	19.2
UP/PH:50/50	125	19.6
PH	287	22.2

Fig.3. $Tan \delta$ vs temperature curves for UP, PH and UP/PH cast resin by DMA

Fig.4. Δ LOI of UP, PH and UP/PH blends

Fig.5(a).HRRversus with time for UP,PH and U/PH cast resin

Fig.5(c). %Mass versus with time for UP,PH and UP/PH cast resin

Fig.5(b). RSR versus with time for UP,PH and UP/PH cast resin

Fig.6. Stress-strain curve for GFRC of UP and UP/PH resin blends under tensile mode

Table 3.Cone results of cast resin

Sample	TTI (s)	FO (s)	PHRR (kW/m ²)	TPHRR (s)	THR (MJ/m ²)	EHC (MJ/kg)	TSR ((m ² /s)/m ²)	Residual mass (%)
UP	36±1	180 ± 6	1130±34	112±3	82.7±2	20.4±0.2	4640±166	1.7±1.2
UP/PH:80/20	39±1	186±2	1035±15	110±4	74.0±3	20.1±0.1	4182±107	7.1±1.0
UP/PH:70/30	38±1	188±3	953±11	100±1	71.1±4	19.6±0.5	3930±140	8.5±1.5
UP/PH:60/40	39±1	204±3	892±4	107±1	69.3±2	20.4±0.2	3974±14	15.2±0.9
UP/PH:50/50	35±0	208±1	809±8	103±7	66.9±2	20.4±0.4	3516± 53	17.1±0.4
PH	49±2	218±2	720±7	97±3	54.7±2	20.2±0.1	2653±42	21±0.2

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Table.4 UL -94 test results for UP and UP/PH co-blended GRFC

Sample	Horizontal burning rate (mm/min)	UL94 rating		Vertical burning rate (mm/min)	Dripping
		Horizontal burning test	Vertical burning test		
UP	17±0.1	HB	Fail	70±2.3	None
UP/PH:70/30	13±0.2	HB	Fail	57±0.2	None
UP/PH:60/40	12±0.3	HB	Fail	49±2.8	None
UP/PH:50/50	11±0.1	HB	Fail	32±0.2	None

Table.5. Normalised mechanical properties of GFRCs with respect to fibre volume fraction of control UP composite

Samples	Thickness (mm)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Impact modulus (GPa)
UP	2.2	17.0±0.2	17.0±0.2	13.1±0.2
UP/PH:70/30	2.2	15.9±0.8 (-1.5)	15.9±0.8 (-1.1)	13.7±0.4 (+0.6)
UP/PH:60/40	2.3	15.7±0.6 (-1.2)	15.7±0.6 (-1.3)	14.0±0.3 (+0.9)
UP/PH:50/50	2.4	15.8±0.4 (+0.5)	15.8±0.4 (-1.2)	13.0±0.5 (-0.1)

Note: The values in parentheses are change in value w.r.t. control UP sample, (+) denoting increase and (-) decrease.